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A CNN-Based Approach for Understanding SAR Backscattering of Bare Soil

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Abstract

Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data is widely used for remotely sensing the geometry of a scene, but also for the estimation of parameters like biomass or moisture in various applications. However, SAR data is noisy and difficult to interpret for a non-expert. In this paper, we propose an approach for Understanding the SAR backscattering for the case of bare soil, when two parameters of high interest for agriculture are known - soil surface roughness (SSR) and soil moisture (SM). Starting from these two parameters, in parallel, we generate (i) radar signal backscattering coefficients using a physics-based model and (ii) synthetic color images of bare soil. Then we use these data to train a machine learning (ML) model to predict the backscattering coefficients. We show that the used model is capable of predicting the vertical-vertical (VV) and vertical-horizontal (VH) coefficients with an acceptable error and emphasize the explainability of the results due to the synthetic images used for training the model.

1 Introduction

Earth Observation (EO) technologies, specifically, remote sensing (RS) systems attached to various spaceborne, aircraft, unmanned aerial vehicles, static and moving ground units, and crowdsensing platforms are proven to be effective in agricultural monitoring and decision-making [1]. SAR is of particular interest for remotely sensing the geometry of a scene and estimate important parameters such as biomass [2], soil moisture [3], plant structure [4], surface elevation changes [5], [6], etc.

Soil is the foundation for the current agriculture, and it is a complex combination of minerals, organic matter, water, air, and microorganisms, and it is fundamental in agriculture. SM is one of the most important

factors in the hydrological cycle, weather conditions, plant growth, nutrient cycling, etc. [7], [8]. SM is a key parameter in irrigation management [9], crop yield prediction [10], weather models [11], and more.

Predicting SM with RS technologies has been an active research area in the last few decades. SAR is day-and-night, all-weather imaging technology that uses the motion of the deployed platform (e.g., satellites) to expand the aperture of the radar. SAR uses microwaves which are capable of penetrating through clouds and even vegetation layers depending on the wavelength-to-object relationship [12], [13]. Two main parameters affect the reflected radar backscattering: i) the geometrical properties of the scene, and ii) the dielectric constant. In SAR applications for bare soil, these properties can be described by SSR and SM parameters, since SSR is related to the variability of surface geometric features, and SM is strictly linked to the dielectric constant of the soil [14], [15]. However, SAR data is difficult to interpret for non-experts.

Electromagnetic models, particularly surface radar backscatter models, are designed to simulate interactions between the radar signal and target, and, by inverting them, estimation of parameters like SM and SSR is possible [16]. These models can be divided into three categories: empirical, semi-empirical, and physics-based [17]. Empirical approaches, like the one adopted in the Dubois model [18], and semi-empirical ones, such as the Oh models [19] rely on extensive ground-truth data for calibration. The physics-based models are IEM [20] and derived versions of it, such as IEM_B by Baghdadi [21], and the Advanced Integral Equation Model [22]. Although physics-based models simulate SAR interactions to some extent, they rely on rigorous theoretical formulations and multiple simplifying assumptions. By contrast, CNNs and other neural networks capture nonlinearities, adapt easily to new regions, scale efficiently, and deliver fast inference.

In this study, we generated Gaussian-correlated surface profiles that include varying SSR and SM parameter values, and encoded them into computer-generated color images, which are the inputs for the CNN model. Backscattering estimations for vertical-vertical (VV, co-polarized) and vertical-horizontal (VH, cross-polarized) polarization channels from IEM simulation were used as target variables in the CNN model. Moreover, with the foundation of this research, we plan to integrate more complex scenes and eventually replace computer-generated, synthetic images with real ones.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II describes data and methodology, Section III presents results and discussions, and finally, Section IV concludes the paper.

2 Methodology

The methodology includes bare soil synthetic image generation with varying SSR and SM values, and in parallel, estimated backscattering values with IEM simulation. Further, images are used as input to the CNN, and backscattering values from the IEM simulation are used as target values. Fig. 1 shows the block diagram of the method.

Figure 1: Block diagram of the proposed approach.

2.1 Numerical Surface Generation

The choice of surface is important for IEM simulations for SAR. Gaussian and exponentially-correlated surfaces are commonly employed due to their ability to approximate the natural terrains. Gaussian correlated surfaces are particularly suitable because of their mathematical tractability and capacity to represent various roughness levels. There are two important parameters to describe the SSR, root mean square of surface heights (σ) and correlation length (l). σ parameter describes the vertical surface height variations while l is to capture the horizontal profile of the surface. We closely followed the technique described in [23] to generate a Gaussian-like surface. C_k is a Gaussian correlated sequence of surface heights that can be written as:

$$C_k = \sum_{j=-M}^M W_j X_{j+k} \quad (1)$$

where W_j 's are the Gaussian filter weights and X_{j+k} is random normal input sequence. The summation represents the convolution operation over the filter width. Since

$$E \{C_k C_{k+i}\} = \sum_j \sum_n W_j W_n \{X_{j+k} X_{n+k+i}\} \quad (2)$$

and $\{X_k\}$ is an independent sequence, we can write

$$E \{X_{j+k} X_{n+k+i}\} = \begin{cases} 0, & j \neq n+i \\ 1, & j = n+i \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

It follows that

$$E \{C_k C_{k+i}\} = \sum_j W_j W_{j-1} \quad (4)$$

Starting with the expected value $E \{C_k C_{k+i}\}$ in Eq. (2), we can simplify it using the independence property of the input sequence X_k . Since the input sequence consists of independent random normal variables, their expected product (Eq. (3) = 1) only when the indices match ($j = n+i$) and 0 otherwise. This simplification reduces the double summation to a single summation $\sum_j W_j W_{j-i}$ in Eq. (4). The final form shows that the autocorrelation of the generated surface is determined solely by the convolution of the filter weights with themselves. It means we can design our filter weights by taking the inverse Fourier transform of the square root of our desired surface spectrum. For example, let the correlation function be Gaussian:

$$\rho = \exp [-(j/l)^2] \quad (5)$$

Its spectrum is $\rho_s = 1\sqrt{\pi} \exp (-l^2 f^2/4)$ and the square root of ρ_s is

$$(\rho_s)^{1/2} = (l\sqrt{\pi})^{1/2} \exp (-l^2 f^2/8) \quad (6)$$

The inverse of Eq. (5) is the filter weight and can be written as

$$W_j = \left(\frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}l} \right)^{1/2} \exp [-2(j/l)^2] \quad (7)$$

Fig. 2. illustrates the two surface profiles over a distance ($L = 200$), where surface A represents a rougher surface ($\sigma = 2$) than surface B ($\sigma = 0.7$) and $l = 4$ in both cases. All the surface parameters are in the centimeters (cm) unit of measurement.

2.2 Moisture content of the soil

Another important parameter in SAR simulation is the soil dielectric permittivity, which is directly related to the moisture content of the soil [14], [15]. We considered SM from 1% to 50% with step size = 1 in the IEM simulation as well as input to the CNN. Since we are using images to represent the bare soil data, the color aspect is a way to embed the moisture content. Shades of brown from light for dry soil to dark brown for wet soil were used.

Let m_p be the soil moisture percentage, where $m_p \in [0, 50]$. The moisture factor f_m is normalized to $[0, 1]$ range:

$$f_m = \min \left(\max \left(\frac{m_p}{50}, 0 \right), 1 \right) \quad (8)$$

The RGB color components for visualizing soil moisture are then calculated as follows:

Figure 2: Two sample surface profiles with $\sigma = 2$ and $\sigma = 0.7$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 R(f_m) &= 210 - f_m(210 - 101) = 210 - 109f_m \\
 G(f_m) &= 180 - f_m(180 - 67) = 180 - 113f_m \\
 B(f_m) &= 140 - f_m(140 - 33) = 140 - 107f_m
 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

where $R(f_m)$, $G(f_m)$, and $B(f_m)$ represent the red, green, and blue color components, respectively, each rounded to the nearest integer. The resulting color transitions from a lighter brown $(R, G, B) = (210, 180, 140)$ at 0% moisture to a darker brown $(R, G, B) = (101, 67, 33)$ at 50% moisture (see Fig. 3).

Figure 3: SM content is coded using a color gradient from light beige to deep brown, representing soil moisture resolution from 0% to 50% saturation.

2.3 IEM Data and CNN

IEM data was generated using IEM [20] simulation, and it contains 50 moisture values from 1% to 50% for each SSR value from 0.1 to 2 totaling 1000 estimated VV and VH backscattering values each; further, these values were used as target variables in the CNN. We used CNN, particularly, a deep residual learning with ResNet-18, which overcomes the vanishing gradient

problem and is mainly designed for image classification tasks [24]. However, by modifying the last layer, it was adapted for the regression task. It is important to note that two independent ResNet-18 models were used to predict one specific output (VV and VH) because a single model performed less accurately when predicting two outputs. This can be explained by the fact that VV and VH usually have different magnitudes and variances, which causes one channel to suppress the other, thus decreasing the model’s accuracy. Additionally, VV is being more sensitive to soil parameters while VH captures more of the volume scattering; thus, the filters of a single model struggle to specialize. Moreover, after encoding the SSR and SM values into the images, they were resized to $224 \times 224 \times 3$ and split into training and testing with 80% and 20% respectively. The model uses the MSE loss function, Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001, and the model is trained over 50 epochs.

3 Results and Discussions

Fig. 4. shows the generated bare soil synthetic images with various roughness and moisture values.

Figure 4: Generated bare soil synthetic images with various roughness and moisture levels.

We evaluated the model fitness using the weighted performance-generalization metric, which is a composite score that considers test loss magnitude, training loss magnitude, and their relative difference. The model fitness composite score S_c is computed as:

$$S_c = w_t \mathcal{L}_{test} + w_{tr} \mathcal{L}_{train} + w_g \left(\frac{2|\mathcal{L}_{test} - \mathcal{L}_{train}|}{\mathcal{L}_{test} + \mathcal{L}_{train}} \right) \quad (10)$$

S_c combines weighted test loss ($w_t = 0.4$), training loss ($w_{tr} = 0.3$), and their gap ($w_g = 0.3$). Lower scores indicate better model performance and generalization, guiding the model selection.

The scatter plots in Fig. 5. present the relationship between predicted and actual backscattering coefficients in dB. The unity line serves as a ref-

erence for perfect prediction, while the coefficient of determination (R^2) quantifies the model's explanatory power. The Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) provides another measure of prediction accuracy in dB.

Figure 5: Scatter plot showing predicted values against actual values with the ideal prediction line (red dashed). BSC stands for backscattering.

Fig. 6. shows the error distribution for train and test sets in VV and VH polarization as a histogram and Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) (red line). The automatic binning algorithm responds to VH's higher variance (std error 1.0661 dB) in cross-polarization by choosing fewer bins, while VV's more consistent co-polarized scattering produces a smoother, more normally distributed error pattern.

Table 1 shows the composite score value at the best model, along with the train and test losses.

Figure 6: Histogram and KDE of prediction errors.

Table 1: Train and test performance metrics for VV and VH channels.

Metric (MSE)	VV (dB)	VH (dB)
Final Training Loss	1.3195	3.3288
Final Test Loss	0.9240	0.9298
Best Training Loss	1.0194	2.1891
Best Test Loss	0.2740	0.3544
Training Loss at Best Model	1.0983	2.1891
Test Loss at Best Model	0.6596	1.3439
Composite Score at Best Model	0.7431	1.3378
Best Model Epoch	48/50	41/50

4 Conclusion

Accurate estimation of SM and SSR through SAR backscattering is important for environmental monitoring and agricultural management. While SAR data is noisy and difficult to interpret for non-experts, we developed a deep-learning framework that achieves acceptable accuracy in both VV and VH polarized backscattering coefficients. We developed method that encodes SSR ($\sigma = [0.1 - 2]$) and SM (1-50%) as synthetic color RGB images, creating spatial dependencies that capture surface complexity. We employed the ResNet architecture and modified it for a regression task. We

trained and tested the model with a total of 1000 images ($224 \times 224 \times 3$) to predict VV and VH polarization backscattering coefficients obtained from IEM simulation. The model achieved a MSE of 0.66 dB for VV polarization and 1.34 dB for VH polarization on the test dataset, and the performance remained consistent across varying SSR and SM. This approach contributes to the explainability of SAR backscattering through the use of synthetic color images of bare soil encoding SSR and SM.

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